

Deliverable 7.1

Report on the environmental and socio-economic drivers, stressors and response of basin-scale Atlantic ecosystem and related ecosystem services

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1 Version History

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2 Executive summary

The Atlantic ocean is a fundamental element in the Earth system, playing a key role in regulating global temperatures, storing heat and carbon dioxide, driving weather patterns and variability, and delivering a number of fundamental ecosystem services: regulating services (e.g. through carbon sequestration and storage), supporting services (e.g. related to biodiversity maintenance and nutrient cycling), provisioning services (e.g. through fisheries), and cultural services.

Ongoing climate change is driving notable alterations in the Atlantic Ocean environment, marine ecosystems and associated services (Garcia-Soto et al., 2021). To gain a deeper insight into the consequences of these changes, it is essential to get a better understanding of their underlying physical drivers. On the other hand, the provision of marine ecosystem services in the Atlantic Ocean is also modulated by socio-economic factors that need to be modelled considering different Shared Socio-economic Pathways.

AtlantEco WP7 included specific activities to improve our knowledge on the status of the Atlantic Ocean looking at both environmental and socio-economic drivers and stressors. The present deliverable is dedicated to report the results obtained within related sub-tasks. It includes the main results that have been detailed in published/submitted papers and also describes some unpublished preparatory work that was fundamental in the selection of the analysis techniques.

The study of the Atlantic Ocean seascape focused on the most relevant signals and ecosystem responses that are detected at different spatial and temporal scales in the observational records and in numerical model outputs. The general aim has been to assess the dominant dynamics, associated patterns of variability and drivers of change through physically reasoned approaches. To achieve this objective, we complemented the study of specific processes and signals occurring in selected sub-regions with basin-scale and global analyses of the dominant modes of variability.

A statistical analysis of basin-scale data highlighted the difficulties in identifying physically consistent modes beyond the first two, even when considering multivariate configurations (section 4.1.1). While this proved useful to intercompare and validate the output of numerical models at different resolutions (section 4.1.1.2), it finally led us to replace the purely statistical analysis of basin-scale data with an empirical stochastic modelling approach at global scale (4.1.2). This technique is able to discriminate internal modes of variability from longer term trends and allows better identification of how the upper ocean is responding to global changes. It revealed the interplay between surface warming, shifts in atmospheric and oceanic circulation, and their connections to the hydrological cycle. This multivariate approach demonstrated that the ocean's response to climate change is more complex than that revealed by individual variables alone, and clearly not limited to a general intensification of ocean stratification impacting nutrient and energy exchange between the euphotic zone and the deep ocean. Specific focus has been put in the description of the variability of Sub Polar Mode Waters formation (from observation-based data, section 4.1.3) and of the physical drivers of nutrient variability in the North Atlantic (from model data, section 4.1.4).

The stochastic modes have been used to reveal the dynamical drivers of observed change in chlorophyll-a (section 4.2.1). A specific study was dedicated to the assessment of the ultra-oligotrophic water expansion in the North Atlantic Subtropical Gyre (from satellite observations, section 4.2.2).

The impact of ongoing changes has been further explored by investigating key controls of two ecosystem services: carbon sequestration and biodiversity maintenance. The former was investigated both through observation-based estimates of physical injection pump of particulate organic carbon (section 4.2.3) and by improving the quantification of century scale carbon sequestration by the biological pump through a model-based approach (section 4.2.4). The latter combined Species Distribution Modeling approaches built on genomic data of plankton obtained from the Tara Ocean expedition with the environmental parameters that define the different niches, with temperature emerging as the primary influential parameter (section 4.2.5).

The analyses of the socio-economic drivers included the specification and conceptualization of different scenarios trends for social and economic stressors. The activity included macro-economic modelling of future trends of the fishery economic production and fishery prices in the different Atlantic regions through ICES model (section 4.3.1). It allowed us to revise the projections on the fishery production growth and to suggest a realistic cap on the global growth of the fishery production based on scientific literature review.

A more general framework to identify trends regarding conceptualization of the services provided by marine ecosystems has been explored through a systematic review of the scientific literature on socio-economic drivers and stressors, drawing on peer-reviewed and quality-indexed academic publications (section 4.3.2). Categorized impacts (e.g. pressures, drivers, stressors, threats, opportunities, benefits) and social transformations have been identified according to IPBES indirect and direct drivers of biodiversity and ecosystem change.

The main findings of our review indicate that the investigation of socio-economic drivers on marine ecosystem services in the Atlantic Ocean is an emerging field, and is strongly focused on empirical data gathering through natural scientific research. Most research investigated individual types of ecosystems situated along the coastlines of the North American, European and West African continents, including intensively used coastal areas, shelf ecosystems and marine areas such as coral reefs highlighting the perceived importance of these areas and ecosystems to scientists working in the field. Furthermore, regulating and material services emerged as most frequently cited.

These findings correspond with the finding that climate change and change in land use were identified as very important socio-economic drivers since their effects are most likely to be noticed in ecosystems which are most sensitive to associated impacts and which are of material importance to human societies. Despite this, social science studies exploring the links between socio-economic drivers and their effects on marine ecosystem services were lacking in our review.

This document is based on the terms and conditions established in the Grant Agreement (GA) and its Annexes, as well as in the Consortium Agreement (CA).

3 Introduction

One of the major objectives of AtlantEco WP7 was to assess the present status of basin-scale Atlantic ecosystem processes, their patterns of variability and drivers, as well as to gain new knowledge of the processes and interactions required to improve the modelling of past and future scenarios in Atlantic ecosystem services and health. This objective reflects the importance of better understanding and framing the consequences and impacts of climate change on the Atlantic environment, and particularly on its planktonic component, and how this is modifying its seascape and related services.

The Atlantic seascape is shaped by complex physical processes that modulate its thermohaline and wind-driven circulation, including air-sea interactions driving dense water formation, western boundary currents dynamics, mesoscale-to-submesoscale turbulence, coastal upwelling, boundary layer mixing, sediment resuspension and transport, as well as interactions between the shelf and open ocean, such as offshore transport driven by large river plumes. This dynamic system integrates living resources (organisms) and non-living resources (tracers) with biological, chemical, and physical processes intertwined in shaping its structure at local and regional scales, but it is also intimately linked to the changes occurring at the global scale.

Ocean currents and mixing play a key role in transporting nutrients, pollutants, carbon, and food to deeper layers, while also connecting and dispersing species and communities, thereby influencing their biogeographical patterns. Climate change further alters seascape dynamics by modifying stratification and shifting circulation patterns, which affect biodiversity distribution, including key species of commercial interests. To uncover the most critical processes, it is crucial to examine the physical drivers of the changes detected in observational records. This involves focusing on key variables and processes influencing plankton dynamics (though generally described through oversimplified models, such as by looking at chlorophyll concentration as a proxy of phytoplankton, and/or on selected phytoplankton classes/species groupings). The research detailed hereafter tackled this challenging objective by complementing the partial information available from data-driven reconstructions with more complete numerical model output and by leveraging advanced analysis techniques to integrate highly detailed biological samples with environmental variables.

Of course, the provision of marine ecosystem services in the Atlantic Ocean is also strongly influenced by socio-economic factors, and a fundamental step for an improved knowledge-based management of Atlantic Ocean ecosystem resides in identifying socioeconomic indicators/stressors starting from Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSP) database, which includes projections for population and economic development. The analysis of socio-economic drivers carried out within AtlantEco WP7 involved defining and conceptualizing scenario trends for various social and economic stressors, including macro-economic modeling of future trends in fishery economic production and prices across different Atlantic regions. Additionally, a broader framework for identifying trends in the conceptualization of services provided by marine ecosystems was developed through a systematic review of scientific literature on socio-economic drivers and stressors.

4 Work carried out and main results achieved

4.1 Analysis of environmental drivers and stressors

Different topics related to the identification and analysis of environmental trends and variability patterns have been covered and detailed in the following:

- the identification of patterns of variability through Principal Component Analysis
- the multivariate analysis of main trends and dominant patterns of variability based on Linear Inverse Modelling
- the description of interannual variability in SubPolar Mode Water (SPMW) formation

- the identification of the physical drivers of nutrient variability in the North Atlantic Subpolar Gyre

4.1.1 Identification of environmental variability patterns through Principal Component Analysis

4.1.1.1 Observation-based patterns: basin-scale vs global variability

During the first year of the project, exploratory investigations have been dedicated to the estimation and analysis of the multivariate Empirical Orthogonal Function decomposition (a.k.a. Principal Component Analysis, PCA, see Jolliffe, 2002) of basin-scale observation-based environmental data obtained from the European Copernicus Marine Service. The products and variables used for this exercise are those detailed in Buongiorno Nardelli and Iudicone (2024), and several sensitivity tests have been carried out to assess the relevance of different combinations of the state variables.

The analyses were focused on low frequency signals (low-pass filtering weekly data). The state vector considered initially included sea surface temperature (SST) and salinity (SSS), mixed layer depth (MLD), horizontal and vertical components of the kinetic energy at the surface and 100 m, respectively. Both regional signals and global patterns have been analysed, also investigating the sensitivity of the identified modes and temporal signals to the length of the available time series. These first tests evidenced the limits of EOF technique in identifying physically consistent modes, namely the difficulty in correctly discriminating between trending components and interannual/decadal signals.

Figure 1. First multivariate EOF mode (only Atlantic). The multivariate state vector includes, sea surface temperature, sea surface salinity, upper mixed layer depth, intensity of the vertical exchanges at 100 m depth, intensity of the horizontal currents in the upper layer (both defined as the square root of corresponding kinetic energy components).

Figure 2. Second multivariate EOF mode (only Atlantic). The multivariate state vector includes, sea surface temperature, sea surface salinity, upper mixed layer depth, intensity of the vertical exchanges at 100 m depth, intensity of the horizontal currents in the upper layer (both defined as the square root of corresponding kinetic energy components).

Specifically, in the basin-scale analysis we found that only the first two modes could be somehow associated to known processes, but their interpretability was extremely limited. This is due to the difficulty to clearly link estimated temporal amplitudes with known signals: the first mode patterns somehow resemble global linear trends estimated from individual variables, but corresponding amplitude only shows a steep increase after 2011 and a clear maximum in 2016. Similarly, the second mode only displays a peak in correspondence of the negative North Atlantic Oscillation anomaly observed in 2010. The two modes explain about 30% of total variance, a large portion of which is thus distributed across several successive modes that unfortunately do not display any physically interpretable behaviour.

As such, we extended the EOF analysis to the global ocean, to account for large scale dynamics that modulates the Atlantic climate beyond local processes, but then realized that additional new issues emerged. These were related to the fact that EOF modes do eventually mix patterns related to different processes, making it problematic, for example, to properly separate the interannual oscillations/decadal variability in the Pacific (e.g. PDO and ENSO) and eventual trending components. In fact, the estimation of the global trend (which emerged as a relevant contribution to the first EOF mode) was clearly affected by strong signals in the Pacific, whose decadal variability was rather split among several different modes.

Indeed, while we were able to improve the correlation between the second global EOF amplitude and known climatic indexes by applying rotated-EOF analysis, it appeared evident that EOF/PCA application does not provide reliable dynamical mode identification when investigating complex, interactive, or evolving processes as the ones we aim to disentangle within AtlantEco (see also Hannachi et al., 2007). Specifically, by performing pairwise rotations of first two principal components, we could increase the correlation between the second mode amplitude and PDO index from $\rho_{PC2,PDO}=0.76$ to $\rho_{rPC2,PDO}=0.83$, but the amplitude of the first rotated mode still displayed a suspect maximum in 2016 (it should be kept in mind that one of the strongest El Nino events has been recorded in 2015/2016, e.g. Santos et al., 2017). As a consequence, while the same EOF algorithm proved useful to intercompare and validate numerical models at different resolutions (see section 4.1.1.2), a more advanced stochastic empirical modelling technique has been set up and selected for the identification of physically based modes of variability, as detailed in section 4.1.2.

Figure 3. First multivariate EOF mode (Global Ocean). The multivariate state vector includes, sea surface temperature, sea surface salinity, upper mixed layer depth, intensity of the vertical exchanges at 100 m depth, intensity of the horizontal currents in the upper layer (both defined as the square root of corresponding kinetic energy components).

Figure 4. Second multivariate EOF mode (Global Ocean). The multivariate state vector includes, sea surface temperature, sea surface salinity, upper mixed layer depth, intensity of the vertical exchanges at 100 m depth, intensity of the horizontal currents in the upper layer (both defined as the square root of corresponding kinetic energy components).

4.1.1.2 Model data variability patterns

Much of our understanding of ocean variability comes from models. Analysing the modes of variability which act on regional to global spatial scales and on inter-annual to decadal timescales requires a data coverage difficult to obtain with observations, particularly when considering subsurface ocean information. Much of the current generation of CMIP and even HighResMIP models (Roberts et al., 2022), which act as the basis for projections of future climate, do not have a resolution capable of resolving fronts and eddies, particularly poleward of the midlatitudes (Tebaldi et al., 2021 and references therein). More and more models however are surpassing 1/10 resolution (e.g. Moreno-Chamarro et al., 2025). Intercomparison of resolution is therefore crucial for planning model development and quantifying the necessity of resolution increases.

Here, using three configurations of the same CMCC ocean model (GLOB16) at horizontal resolutions of 1° , $1/4^\circ$ and $1/16^\circ$, we isolate the impact of model resolution on the variability of environmental drivers. The model set-up is described in Iovino et al. (2016) and Iovino et al. (2023). The configurations are hereafter labelled as ORCA1, ORCA025 and GLOB16. The number of vertical levels also increases, from 50 in ORCA1/025 to 98 in GLOB16. Here, we study variability through the lens of EOFs (Section 4.1.1.1). As mentioned, EOF can struggle to detect physically consistent modes, particularly when isolating trends from decadal modes. The examples studied here, such as ENSO and sub-polar MLD variability, are known to be distinct from lower-order EOFs, and suitable targets for EOF analysis (e.g. Messie & Chavez et al., 2011; Chen & Tung, 2018). Given the high-resolution of data used here, implementing new techniques (e.g. the multi-variate EOFs) proved to be a technical challenge. Moreover, given the dataset size, it is not possible to calculate global EOFs for GLOB16.

The representation of global-scale modes of climate variability is not sensitive to resolution (Fig. 1). The four EOFs of global SST which contribute most to variability in both ORCA1 and ORCA025 are very similar, and represent ENSO, the Atlantic Multidecadal Oscillation (AMO), the Pacific Decadal Oscillation (PDO) and the North Pacific Gyre Oscillation (NPGO) respectively, in agreement with Messie & Chavez et al. (2011) & Chen & Tung, (2018). The contribution of EOF1 (i.e. ENSO) to total variability reduces from 28.1% to 15.1% from ORCA1 to ORCA025, as the higher-resolution model retains more variability in the lowest-order EOFs (i.e. beyond EOF4; not shown). The clearest differences however are found in the North Atlantic, in the magnitude of variability linked to these climate modes; the difference is most obvious in EOF2 i.e. the AMO. For example, the apparent AMO-related variability in the North Atlantic sub-polar gyre is weaker in ORCA025, and the same model displays a relatively narrow North Atlantic Canary upwelling system.

Figure 5. First four univariate EOF of global annual sea surface temperature, ordered from top to bottom by total explained variability (inset).

Figure 6. First univariate EOF of March mixed layer depth in the Nordic Seas (top). Average surface current speed (middle and average sea ice concentration (bottom)).

To explore further these regional differences in North Atlantic variability, MLD is used. MLD acts as a proxy for both nutrient mixing and water-mass formation, particularly in late winter in the presence of strong winds and an upper layer of unstable cold water (Pickart et al. 1997). The first EOFs of March MLD in each area are now used to represent winter convection. The Nordic Seas are in theory more susceptible to change in resolution, given the Rossby radius of deformation (and thus eddy representation) is closed to the resolution in GLOB16. In ORCA1, there is a wide area of convection covering the entire Greenland gyre, while in ORCA025 this zone is displaced north-eastwards (Fig. 2). In GLOB16 there is further displacement north-eastwards and notably a considerably weaker convection, reaching depths of less than 200m. Such differences transform the role of the Nordic Sea in terms of water mass creation and nutrient availability. The maps of average currents display the stark differences in dynamical processes when resolution is increased (Fig. 3). ORCA1 has a very weak Greenland gyre, and is unable to represent the many finer currents present even in ORCA025. The Norwegian Atlantic current, following the eastern coastline of the basin, is considerably stronger in GLOB16, indicating how Atlantic inflow water through the Faroe Shetland channel is redirected. In particular, the sea ice concentration in the Greenland gyre is higher in ORCA025 and to a greater extent in GLOB16; the presence of sea ice hinders wind-driven convection, and partially explains the displacement of the convection zones in the higher resolution models. This analysis provides an indication of the wide-reaching implications across the region of recreating the detailed network of currents in the Nordic Sea.

Figure 7. First univariate EOF of March mixed layer depth in the Nordic Seas (top) and sub-tropical North Atlantic gyre (bottom).

Moving towards lower latitudes, the impact of resolution on modes of MLD variability is weaker but nonetheless displays important shifts in magnitudes. In the sub-polar gyre (Fig. 4), the origin of subpolar mode water, the models agree on the location of winter convection, although the extent of this region into the sub-polar gyre is greater in ORCA025. Meanwhile, in the sub-tropical gyre, the dipolar variability structure present in ORCA1 decays with resolution (i.e. centred around 20W, 50N).

Overall, the jump from a resolution representing the current generation of climate models (ORCA025) to a sub-0.1 resolution displays the most profound changes in the high-latitudes (e.g. Nordic Sea). At these latitudes the Rossby radius of deformation is similar to the GLOB16 resolution. Determining whether they are improvements (i.e. closer to observations) is rendered more difficult by low resolution of MLD products (for example 1 in de Boyer Montegut et al., 2022). GLOB16 generally narrows the regions of convection, but also in some cases disagrees with the location of these zones. Our results indicate that dynamical processes in current models are insufficient in sub-polar to polar regions, and have profound effects on representation of key environmental stressors such as MLD.

4.1.2 From statistical analysis to stochastic modelling: using data-driven reconstructions to discriminate internal dynamical modes and long-term trends

Both univariate and multivariate statistical techniques can be used to describe temporal and spatial variability patterns, eventually capturing intrinsic dynamical signals. However, as shown in section 4.1.1.1, standard techniques fail to effectively separate long-term trends from internal modes of variability and, by construction, are not able to properly account for autocorrelation within time series data. EOF decomposition does not always produce physically meaningful patterns as it is inherently unable to detect relationships involving wave-like propagating signals or delayed responses. In fact, several widely used climatic indices may also not fully capture the underlying dynamical processes (Compo & Sardeshmukh, 2010; Penland & Matrosova, 2006).

The alternative approach that we have selected to uncover the dominant dynamics of the system and related patterns involves empirically fitting a stochastic model to observed time series. Leveraging the work of Hasselman (1976) on climatic stochastic models, we assumed that state variables can be decomposed into low-frequency and high-frequency components, where responses to nonlinear dynamics decay faster than those of linear dynamics. Under this assumption, the system's evolution can be described using a linearized dynamical operator combined with a white-noise forcing term (Hannachi, 2021a; Hasselmann, 1988; Neumaier & Schneider, 2001; Penland & Sardeshmukh, 1995). Corresponding system of ordinary differential equations represents an autoregressive (AR) process, whose normal modes can be empirically estimated from instantaneous and lagged covariances of the observed state vector time series (Hannachi, 2021b). This approach, known as Linear Inverse Modelling (LIM) (Neumaier & Schneider, 2001; Penland & Sardeshmukh, 1995), is widely referenced in the literature and has been applied here to observation-based reconstructions of the global ocean covering the 1993-2018 period. In particular, we computed and analysed the eigenmodes of the deterministic linear operator, also referred to as Principal Oscillation Patterns (POPs). By estimating POPs, we were able to remove the oscillatory signals from physical

variables. In fact, we found that decadal trends are contaminated by the excitation of internal dynamical modes that cannot be fully discriminated by EOF technique.

With respect to the preliminary work described in section 4.1.1.1, to help the dynamical interpretation of the POP modes, we expanded the set of variables under consideration including also wind stress. We also found that including temporal derivatives into the state vector (which is equivalent to building an autoregressive model of second order) significantly improves the description of the dynamical system. This corresponds to the need of knowing both position and velocity in the phase space to describe the system dynamics, which is a common situation in classical mechanics.

The key findings of POP analysis are that:

- surface warming appears almost twice faster once Pacific oscillations are properly accounted for (see fig.8)
- the response of the upper ocean to global warming involves substantial modification of the atmosphere-ocean interactions, impacting not only upper ocean temperature but also freshwater fluxes, currents, mixing and, in turn, stratification and dense water formation
- oceanic currents are rather being modified than effectively declining: some major current systems are shifted latitudinally, and vertical exchanges are increasing in most western boundary currents, impacting mode water formation and deep ocean heat storage
- heat and salinity trends display different patterns in the upper ocean and in the lower layers, reflecting a much more complex response than an overall stabilizing effect, through changes in the thermohaline circulation.

Figure 8. Patterns and amplitude of the POP trend mode estimated from observation-based dynamical ocean state variables. Sea surface temperature (a), wind stress intensity (b) sea surface salinity (c), upper mixed layer depth (d), intensity of the vertical exchanges at 100 m depth (e), intensity of the horizontal currents in the upper layer (f). (e) and (f) are both defined as the square root of corresponding kinetic energy components. (g) Temporal amplitude of the trend mode.

To better identify the emergent patterns of long-term trends we clustered the different variables' POP patterns through different machine learning algorithms (K-means and K-medoids) to provide a dynamical geography of the changing seascape (figure 9).

Figure 9. K-means clustering of trend patterns estimated from observation-based dynamical ocean state variables. Spatial distribution of the clusters (a). Box plot of characteristic distribution of the state variables for each of the identified clusters (b). Boxes span from the lower quartile to the upper quartile, and lines represent the median values. Whiskers emanate from each box, illustrating the data's overall range. Values for chlorophyll-a are obtained from projected trends and are not used to identify the clusters.

The description of the full set of results is given in *Buongiorno Nardelli and Iudicone* (preprint available at <https://arxiv.org/abs/2405.18981>, paper presently under review on *Sci. Adv.* 2025).

4.1.3 Variability of Subpolar Mode Water formation rates in the North Atlantic

Subpolar Mode Water (SPMW) is a key water mass originating in the North Atlantic. Its formation, influenced by interior ocean mixing, plays a direct role in determining the volume of water contributing to the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC). Using observation-based 3D reconstructions of temperature and salinity and total velocities provided by the Copernicus Marine Service, we estimated SPMW formation rates and volumes within isopycnal layers, while also analysing temporal variability over the 1993-2018 period. These data were analysed within AtlantEco WP7 through a kinematic approach and the results compared to the values obtained through a thermodynamic technique applied by the *University of Bremen*.

The two complementary methods employed to estimate formation rates are: a thermodynamic approach accounting for air-sea interactions and a kinematic approach based on volume transport from the mixed layer into the ocean’s interior, accounting for both 3D advection and mixed layer entrainment and detrainment. This study represented the first application of both approaches to observation-based data in the North Atlantic.

Our findings highlight the significant role of diapycnal mixing in diluting dense waters formed by air-sea fluxes to align with SPMW density ranges. The results reveal a complex interaction of processes, with entrainment driving subduction and obduction rates, and advection mostly influencing smaller-scale dynamics. Interannual variability in SPMW formation volume and location was also identified (see fig.10). Notably, when SPMW formation increases in lighter isopycnal layers, the volume of denser isopycnals decreases, and vice versa. This compensation effect appears linked to a propagation signal, where formation in lighter isopycnal layers impacts denser layers with a lag of several years, underscoring the circulation’s role in shaping SPMW distribution.

Figure 10. Hovmöller diagram of formation rate in the isopycnal bins of the SPMW from 27.1 kg m⁻³ to 27.5 kg m⁻³. Rates were calculated using the kinematic approach (a) with the corresponding components: entrainment (c) and horizontal (d), and using the thermodynamic approach (b). Volume residual and expressed in Sverdrup in e). From Stendardo et al. JGR (2024).

A paper providing details on the datasets selected and techniques adopted, as well as full descriptions of our findings, has been published in the *Journal of Geophysical Research* (Stendardo et al., 2024).

4.1.4 Assessment of physical drivers of nutrient variability in the North Atlantic Subpolar Gyre from numerical model data

Within WP7, an analysis of the physical and biogeochemical output from an eddy-permitting ($1/4^\circ$) global forced biogeochemical hindcast simulation (1958-2015) has been carried out to identify the physical drivers of nutrient variability in the North Atlantic Subpolar Gyre, a region of reported high variability of nutrients. The skill of the model to reproduce the mean state and the variability of observations was evaluated by comparing simulated fields against in situ data of nutrients, salinity and temperature. Model evaluation was extended to the transport of water and biogeochemical properties across hydrographic sections, as well as mixed layer dynamics. Results are summarised in Dale et al. (2023), *BGD*.

4.2 The response of basin-scale Atlantic ecosystems and related services to environmental variability

4.2.1 Ecosystem change drivers: from seascape evolution to phytoplankton response

4.2.1.1 Empirical Orthogonal Function analysis of phytoplankton biomass proxies

The preliminary work dedicated to the identification of the dominant modes of variability in environmental variables through EOFs analysis tools was extended to satellite estimates of chlorophyll-a. This variable has been continuously observed since 1998 and related products, distributed through Copernicus Marine Service, provide the best proxy of the global distribution of phytoplankton biomass based on observations (DOI: 10.48670/moi-00281). The analysis was first carried out only analysing univariate EOFs and successively extended to include in the state vector also the physical variables considered in section 4.1.1.1.

The univariate analysis proved useful to test the potential of separating chlorophyll-a estimates into concentrations associated with micro-, nano- and pico-phytoplankton, starting from Copernicus-Globcolour data. Building on the work of Brewin et al. (2015), three phytoplankton size classes were derived from the resampled CHL_{TOT} data time series. Brewin et al. (2015) employed HPLC-derived CHL measurements, evenly distributed in both space and time, to develop a CHL-based algorithm for phytoplankton size class (PSC) retrieval. This method aligns with the approach of Vidussi et al. (2010), which is grounded in the established relationship between taxonomic groups—characterized by HPLC diagnostic pigments—and their typical or dominant sizes. In this study, we adopted the size classification framework from Sieburth et al. (1978), defining phytoplankton size classes as follows: microphytoplankton (CHL_{MICRO} , cell size $>20 \mu m$), nanophytoplankton (CHL_{NANO} , cell size $2-20 \mu m$), and picophytoplankton (CHL_{PICO} , cell size $<2 \mu m$).

The application of the algorithm by Brewin et al. (2015) provides a clear zonation of phytoplankton size classes based on total chlorophyll concentration (CHL) (Figure 11). The dominant size class varies with the area's trophic regime: small cells (picophytoplankton) dominate in oligotrophic gyres, while larger cells (microphytoplankton) are more prevalent in meso-eutrophic environments, such as shallow waters or regions associated with coastal and equatorial upwelling systems. Nanophytoplankton exhibit an intermediate pattern.

The first EOF modes from all four variables (CHL_{TOT} , CHL_{MICRO} , CHL_{NANO} , CHL_{PICO}) explain roughly one quarter of their total variance and show a strong signal in the tropical Pacific Ocean, significantly anticorrelated with the Pacific Decadal Oscillation index (see table 1).

Figure 11. Average fields of CHL_{TOT} and PSCs from the full time series (1997-10 to 2020-06).

Figure 12. First EOF mode of chlorophyll-a: for total CHL (panels a, b), microphytoplankton-CHL (panels c, d), nanophytoplankton-CHL (panels e, f) and picophytoplankton-CHL (panels g, h). Magenta line superimposed on the temporal evolution of each pattern (panels b, d, f, h) is the Pacific Decadal Oscillation index. To ease the various panels comparison, axes and colorbars were set to the same range.

	$r_{(\text{EOF1} - \text{PDO})}$	$r^2_{(\text{EOF1} - \text{PDO})}$	1 st mode [%]	2 nd mode [%]
CHL _{TOT}	-0.894	0.799	23.4	13.5
CHL _{MICRO}	-0.881	0.776	23.0	13.3
CHL _{NANO}	-0.905	0.820	24.9	13.3
CHL _{PICO}	-0.890	0.792	27.5	13.1

Table 1. Correlation between first mode temporal evolutions of total CHL and CHL of each PSC with the Pacific Decadal Oscillation index. Last two columns refer to the percentage of explained variance by the first and second mode for each variable.

Notably, the spatial patterns of the first EOF modes of single phytoplankton classes resemble those of total chlorophyll concentration, albeit with differing intensities, reflecting the respective role of each class in driving overall phytoplankton variability. Despite these minor differences, the temporal patterns of all size classes are strikingly similar and inversely correlated with the PDO index. Therefore, for successive analyses aimed at identifying the impact of physical drivers on phytoplankton response, only total chlorophyll-a has been considered.

In fact, we also applied multivariate EOF decomposition including Chlorophyll-a as an additional variable (thus aiming to identify co-variability patterns), but the estimated modes still faced the same challenges in interpretability as when using the physical variables alone (in particular the impossibility to correctly separate interannual oscillations from long-term trend)..

4.2.1.2 Projecting chlorophyll data on physical Principal Oscillation Patterns

Instead of carrying out the multivariate statistical analyses of co-variability among physical and biological variables, we thus decided to first identify the dynamical modes of the physics (see section 4.1.2) and only after retrieving corresponding temporal amplitudes, we projected the biological variable on them (fig. 13). Specifically, we projected chlorophyll-a data (a proxy for phytoplankton abundance) onto the POP trend mode and analysed the physical processes driving the observed changes. As such, we were not pretending to define the dynamical regimes looking at chlorophyll variance, but rather only considering the part of the chlorophyll signal that is directly impacted by physically driven interannual variations. This is a much more correct approach considering that plankton does not impact physics (at least to first order) and represents in fact an important conceptual advance.

Figure 13. Patterns of chlorophyll-a projected trends. Chlorophyll-a variable is preliminarily transformed through a logarithm to better resolve its dynamical range.

To explore the physical mechanisms driving the changes in marine phytoplankton, we began by clustering the trend patterns observed across the six physical variables (Fig. 9) and then analysed the chlorophyll-a response within each cluster. By presenting this novel dynamical geography of seascape change, we were able to identify the local physical drivers of observed trends in chlorophyll concentration, extending far beyond the effects of temperature-driven stratification increase. Observed trends in chlorophyll concentration respond to distinct local

physical drivers that are well identified by machine learning clustering. A detailed discussion of the results is provided in *Buongiorno Nardelli and Iudicone* (preprint available at <https://arxiv.org/abs/2405.18981>, paper presently under review on *Sci. Adv.* 2025).

4.2.2 Ultra-Oligotrophic Waters Expansion in the North Atlantic Subtropical Gyre

Oceanic subtropical gyres play a vital role in the global carbon cycle due to their vast size, despite being characterized by oligotrophic waters. Over recent decades, the North Atlantic Subtropical Gyre (NASTG) has undergone the most rapid expansion of oligotrophic waters globally, driven by ocean warming. In this study, we examined the changes in the trophic regime of the NASTG using 21 years (1998–2018) of satellite chlorophyll-a data, alongside additional variables such as Sea Surface Temperature (SST), optical backscatter coefficients (bbp), Secchi disk depth (z_{SD}), and Mixed Layer Depth (MLD). Specifically, we analysed the spatial and temporal variability of waters with the lowest chlorophyll concentrations ($CHL \leq 0.04 \text{ mg m}^{-3}$) and assessed inter-annual variability in key environmental factors. The findings reveal a spatial expansion and increased frequency of these ultra-oligotrophic waters, indicating a shift in the NASTG toward a predominantly quasi-permanent ultra-oligotrophic state, thereby confirming the progression of ocean desertification (fig.14), confirming and detailing what found in the patterns of chlorophyll-a projected trends (section 4.2.1.2).

Figure 14. Spatial annual occurrence per year of surface CHL (in mg m^{-3}) less or equal 0.04 mg m^{-3} for the period 1998-2018 in the subtropical North Atlantic region. (Leonelli et al., GRL, 2022)

A paper describing the assessment of the ultra-oligotrophic waters expansion in the North Atlantic Subtropical Gyre revealed by 21 years of satellite observations has been published in *Geophysical Research Letters* (Leonelli et al., 2022).

4.2.3 Key controls of ecosystem services “Carbon sequestration”: observation-based estimates of physical injection pump of organic carbon

The ocean’s biological carbon pump has traditionally been studied by focusing on the export of organic carbon through sinking particles and vertically migrating organisms. However, despite increasing awareness of the role of dynamical pathways in carbon export, such as mixing and advection, global observation-based estimates of their contribution remain scarce. Within AtlantEco, we utilized a 4D data-driven time series (1997–2018) of particulate organic carbon (POC) concentrations and ocean circulation distributed by Copernicus Marine Service to quantify the physical particle injection pump (PPIP). We analysed the contributions of entrainment and horizontal/vertical advection across mesoscale to large-scale processes (fig. z15).

Figure 15: Geographical variability of PPIP: total (a), entrainment/detrainment (b), horizontal advection (c) and vertical advection (d).

Our results show that the physical injection pump, on average, exports less than 0.1 Pg of POC per year (when eddy diffusivity is neglected). This estimate drops to less than one-third when using climatological POC values instead of weekly data, underscoring the importance of the interplay between the POC annual cycle and mixed-layer dynamics in driving net carbon export. Interannual variations in export are linked to a combination of the El Niño–Southern Oscillation and the Southern Annular Mode, pointing to a dynamic connection with intermediate and mode water formation signals in the Southern Ocean (fig. 16).

The description of the full set of results is given in *Bellacicco et al.* (preprint available at <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-4887998/v1>, paper presently under review on *Nat.Comm.* 2025).

Figure 16. Time-series of POC exports driven by ocean dynamics and climatic indexes. In panel a: black lines is the total PPIP, red line is the POC export due to entrainment, green lines indicates the POC export due to horizontal advection, and blues lines is the vertical advection contribution in driving POC export. Panel b the same as above but using a single 3D POC climatology. Panel c shows the SAM (in blue) and ONI (in orange) climate indexes normalized.

4.2.4 Key controls of ecosystem services “Carbon sequestration”: model-based quantification of century scale carbon sequestration by the biological pump

The biological pump refers to the ensemble of mechanisms transferring carbon from the sunlit surface ocean to depth. The deeper the carbon is exported the longer it is shielded from exchanges with the atmosphere. Previous assessments were based on a fixed horizon, usually 1000 m. Ricour et al. (2023, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41561-023-01318-9>) developed an innovative approach to estimate the century-scale carbon sequestration flux driven by the ocean’s biological pump. By combining model-derived estimates of the fraction of water at varying depths remaining isolated from the atmosphere for more than 100 years (f_{100}) with particulate organic carbon (POC) fluxes, the study identified three primary biological pump pathways: gravitational settling, diurnal/seasonal vertical migration, and physical mixing. Together, these pathways contribute to an estimated global sequestration flux of 0.9–2.6 Pg C yr⁻¹, which is approximately six times higher than previous estimates that focused solely on fluxes below fixed depth horizons (e.g., 1,000–2,000 m). These findings provide a much-needed revision of the ocean’s natural carbon sequestration potential.

As illustrated in Figure 17, each pathway operates within distinct depth ranges. The gravitational pump reaches the deepest depths, potentially transporting organic carbon to the seafloor, while diurnal vertical migration by zooplankton typically extends to ~600 m, and seasonal migration can exceed 1,400 m. Physical mixing redistributes carbon through seasonal shoaling, deepening of the mixed layer, and subduction processes, contributing significantly to the flux in shallower waters. Together, these processes enhance carbon sequestration across the

water column, with upper-ocean sequestration (above 1,000 m) accounting for a significant portion of the total flux.

The study's novel model-based approach, termed "continuous vertical sequestration" (CONVERSE), emphasizes the role of upper-ocean processes, previously underestimated, in contributing to long-term carbon storage. This perspective is particularly relevant for evaluating the efficiency of Carbon Dioxide Removal (CDR) strategies aimed at enhancing the biological pump's strength and efficiency. By integrating depth-specific and geographic variability, the model offers a robust framework for assessing the potential of ocean-based carbon mitigation efforts on climatically significant timescales.

Figure 17: Schematic illustration of the carbon export and sequestration mechanisms of the biological pump. a, Maximum depths to which six carbon export mechanisms transport POC and DOC, and the carbon pump to which each belongs (values are taken from table 2 of ref. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2021.780052>). b, Combined action of the three pumps on F_{remin} : one part of the POC flux is remineralized to CO_2 , and another part is solubilized to DOC by bacteria or released as DOC by grazers, after which most of this DOC is remineralized. The POC flux from migrants to the gravitational pump consists of faecal pellets and remains of migrating organisms. BCP, biological carbon pump.

4.2.5 Key controls of ecosystem services “Biological diversity maintenance”

We investigated the feasibility of employing Species Distribution Modeling (SDM) approaches on genomic data of plankton collected during the Tara Ocean expedition. Rather than focusing on individual species or taxonomic groups, our approach tested the validity of niche models at a broader 'meta-community' scale, referred to as meta-genomic provinces. These provinces were previously defined (doi: 10.7554/eLife.78129) by clustering metagenomic data based on similarities in small DNA fragments known as k-mers. Our central hypothesis was that sufficient genomic similarity among planktonic communities within these provinces would reflect shared environmental niches for at least some of the organisms.

The results supported this hypothesis, demonstrating the existence of environmental niches for 27 meta-genomic provinces. Importantly, plankton were sampled across six size classes, necessitating separate niche calculations for each size fraction. This finding highlighted that each geographic sampling site could be associated with up to six provinces and, consequently, six distinct niches, corresponding to different size fractions of plankton. This initial analysis revealed a clear geographical structuring of plankton communities into climato-genomic provinces, emphasizing the influence of environmental factors on plankton distribution patterns. We successfully mapped the geographical locations of these niches across the six size fractions, providing a comprehensive view of the spatial distribution of meta-genomic provinces (see Figure 18).

To extend this analysis and provide a unified perspective on plankton distribution that transcends size-specific differences, we applied the Phate algorithm (doi: 10.1038/s41587-019-0336-3). This innovative dimensionality reduction technique enabled the integration of the entire dataset into a single map, revealing a globally latitudinal distribution of planktonic communities. This visualization aligns with established environmental gradients, such as temperature and nutrient availability, and highlights the macroecological drivers of plankton biogeography. Further analysis of the global structure showed that plankton communities could be categorized into either four or seven major clusters, depending on the resolution of clustering (see Figure 19).

Furthermore, this approach enabled the identification of environmental parameters defining these niches. Among these properties, temperature emerged as the primary influential parameter for niche definition (in 19 out of 27 niches), albeit with a relative contribution averaging 22.6%. These findings were published in Nature Climate Change (doi: 10.1038/s41558-022-01314-8) and were the subject of a 'news & views' commentary by J.R. Seymour ('Forecasting ocean microbiome shifts. Nat Microbiol 7, 747-748 (2022) <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41564-022-01140-w>).

These findings provide novel insights into the interplay between genomic and environmental factors shaping the global distribution of plankton. By combining SDM approaches, metagenomic data, and advanced computational tools like Phate, this study lays a foundation for future research on marine biodiversity and its responses to environmental changes.

Figure 18: Global biogeographies of size-structured plankton climato-genomic provinces projected (from article doi: 10.1038/s41558-022-01314-8) . a–f, Maps showing biogeographies of metazoans enriched (180–2,000 μm) (a), small metazoans enriched (20–180 μm) (b), protist enriched (5–20 μm) (c), protist enriched (0.8–5 μm) (d), bacteria enriched (0.22–3 μm) (e) and viruses enriched (0–0.2 μm) (f) size fraction. At each grid point of the maps, the dominant province is represented using a darkness of colour proportional to its presence probability. Dots represent areas of uncertainty (where the delta of probability between the dominant and another province is inferior to 0.5). Simple biogeographies are observed in large size fractions ($>20 \mu\text{m}$) with a partitioning in three major oceanic areas: tropico-equatorial, temperate and polar. More complex geographic patterns and patchiness are observed in smaller size fractions.

Figure 19 Present day combined size class biogeographies using the PHATE algorithm. (a) Combined size class biogeography using PHATE algorithm partitioned in 4 clusters. Each grid point is associated to a color depending on its

PHATE coordinates (using three axes). Each coordinate is respectively assigned to a given degree of color between 0 and 255 according to equation (3) (either red green or blue depending on the axis). (b) Combined size class biogeography using PHATE algorithm partitioned in 7 clusters overlaid with Antarctic Circumpolar Current boundaries⁸ (black). Colors are the same as in (a).

The drivers and patterns of species diversity of plankton functional groups (PFGs) have been assessed by ranking the environmental drivers of global biodiversity patterns, and also analyzing their co-variance with Net Primary Production. (Benedetti et al., 2023, <https://academic.oup.com/plankt/article/45/6/832/7308688>). The environmental drivers of pteropod and foraminifera biomass have also been investigated (Knecht et al., 2023, <https://agupubs.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1029/2022GB007685>). Additional work has been carried out to include filter-feeding gelatinous macrozooplankton in a global marine biogeochemical model (Clerc et al., 2023, <https://doi.org/10.5194/bg-20-869-2023>, 2023).

4.3 Socio-economic drivers and stressors

4.3.1 Macro-economic assessment of socio-economic drivers, stressors, and impacts

To address socio-economic drivers and stressors that are relevant for the evolution of marine ecosystems we conduct a macro-economic scenario simulation assessment until 2050. We use the multi-country, multi-sector recursive-dynamic Computable General Equilibrium (CGE) model ICES (Inter-temporal Computable Equilibrium System) (Parrado and Decian 2014; Standardi et al 2023) to identify future trends in the fishery sector for different regions in the Atlantic ocean and the world. The ICES model has been extensively applied to the macro-economic assessment of climate change impacts. A dedicated website of the ICES model is available at <https://www.icesmodel.org/>. The model version used in Atlanteco is calibrated on the Social Accounting Matrices (SAMs) of GTAP 10 database (Aguar et al 2019) for the reference year 2014. The GTAP global database includes economic information for more than 140 countries in the world and 60 sectors covering all the economic system. The theoretical structure of the CGE model is based on representative optimizing agents which maximise or minimise objective functions subject to specific constraints. Representative households in each region maximise utility coming from consumption of goods subject to budget constraints. Representative firms in each region and sector minimise costs subject to technological constraints. When an exogenous shock hits the economic system, demand and supply change together with market prices and economic agents adjust their decisions in terms of consumption and production, export and imports. A new equilibrium is then reached.

Given the importance of the fishery sector in this study we provide a graphical representation of the sector in Figure 20. In each region total production is made of a composite Z and intermediate inputs such as fish feed, transport equipment coming from the industrial sectors and services activities linked to the fishery sector. The composite Z includes labour, natural resources and the capital/energy bundle. Perfect complementarity is assumed between the composite Z and intermediate inputs. Labour, capital/energy and natural resources can be substituted each other to some extent. However, it should be noted that the substitutability within the composite Z in the fishery sector is limited by the presence of the natural resources. Natural resources in the fishery sector represent the economic value of the fish resource and cannot be easily substituted with labour and capital in the production process. This does not take place in other manufacture and service activities which use only labour and the capital/energy bundle as main factors of production in the composite Z. The presence of natural resources and its low substitutability with the other factors of production have important macro-economic implications, especially for future patterns in fishery price.

Figure 20: production structure of the fishery sector in the ICES model

The experiment design starts with historical calibration of GDP and population in the period 2014-2020 using data from the World Bank (WB, 2024). Historical fishery production in the same period has been calibrated using data from the Food and Agriculture Organization database (FAOSTAT, 2024). After historical calibration the experiment design consists in the construction of socio-economic baseline scenarios over the period 2020-2050. For this we retrieve from the SSP database GDP and population projections up to 2050 (Riahi et al 2017) to calibrate SSP2 and SSP5 (O'Neill et al 2015). SSP2 is a middle of the road socio-economic scenario in which Global South exhibits higher economic and demographic growth than those in developed regions. The SSP5, on the other hand, is characterised by strong economic growth at the global level, higher than that in SSP2. Catch-up in terms of GDP per capita between Global South and developed regions is more pronounced in SSP5 than in SSP2 because Global South is growing considerably in economic terms and is also able to slow down the demographic growth. As SSP5 foresees high economic growth but also substantial fossil fuel consumption, we associate it to RCP8.5. The middle of the road scenario SSP2 is instead linked to the RCP4.5 emission scenario.

Usually, in CGE modelling economic activities are free to grow endogenously driven mainly by GDP and populations future projections. Essentially, technological progress, demographic growth and capital accumulation via household saving put no limit to the expansion of the economic sectors. A novelty of this study consists in introducing ecological limits on fishery development. This is done by imposing a biophysical production constraint in the fishery production of the CGE model and calibrating the maximum growth of the global fishery production using a sector specific productivity parameter. As a sensitivity test in the SSP2-RCP4.5 we assume 3 cases: free fishery production expansion up to 2050, 25% global production growth in the period 2020-2050 and 10% growth. In SSP5-RCP8.5 we assume two cases: free expansion and 10% global growth of fishery production. Therefore, overall we build 5 baseline scenarios: namely SSP2-RCP4.5 no limit, SSP2-RCP4.5 25% limit, SSP2-RCP4.5 10% limit, SSP5-RCP8.5 no limit and SSP5-RCP8.5 10% limit. For the identification of the limits we refer to Costello et al (2020), Blanchard and Novaglio (2024) and FAO (2024). In the baseline scenario SSP5-RCP8.5 we consider only the 10% limit on the global fishery expansion because this is also the SSP where the management of environmental resources could be more problematic.

Figure 21 shows the fishery production trends in the period 2020-2050 in the baseline scenarios of SSP2 and SSP5 with different assumptions on global fishery expansion. We can immediately note that in the case of no limit in the global growth of the fishery sector, all regions increase the fishery production in both SSP2 and SSP5. Clearly, fishery production will increase more in the Global South because in the SSP scenarios GDP per capita of the Global South is expected to converge to some extent to the GDP per capita of developed regions in the future. However, fishery expansion driven by GDP and population projections in the SSPs implies unrealistic growth of the fishery sector. At the global level about 77% in the period 2020-2050 in SSP2 and 165% in SSP5 in the same period. These patterns are even much stronger for some regions in the Global South. Overall, this seems not consistent with ecological constraints on fish biomass stock.

Therefore, we exogenously impose in the CGE model a 10% and 25% global fishery expansion over the period 2020-2050. In these cases, the picture of regional fishery trends changes drastically, especially with the more binding constraint of 10%. Regions in the Global South, in particular African regions will still be able to increase their fishery production but the regions in the North, in particular Europe, will decrease substantially their fishery production. The reason for these opposite patterns depends again on the GDP projections of SSPs. Technological progress is expected to be stronger in the Global South and there will be a catching-up in the overall economic system (including the fishery sector) between developing and developed regions. The problem now is that the global cake of the fishery sector is getting smaller and smaller because of the ecological constraints. As a consequence, the regions that have already reached a high level of development and are closed to their technological frontier will exhibit negative percent change in the fishery production. This result is evident if we look at the top and bottom performances in terms of fishery trends in Table 2.

Another important consequence of the introduction of biophysical limits in the CGE model is the effect on global fishery prices. Introducing these limits is equivalent to put a cap on the global supply of fish products. On the other hand, the global demand will continue to raise because the population is increasing, and people are becoming richer. The obvious result is a very strong increment in the global fishery price when these ecological limits are included in the analysis (Table 3). It is also interesting to note that even in case of no limits, fish prices increase a lot because the growth of fishery sector is limited in general by the natural resource and its low substitutability with the other production factors.

In conclusion, the macro-economic simulations suggest that GDP targets of SSPs may imply unrealistic growth of the fishery sector if ecological constraints are not taken into account in the macro-economic model. Also, if no major technological breakthrough will occur and consumer preferences will remain stable, fish prices will skyrocket in all scenarios, including scenarios where no global limit is set. This depends on the nature itself of the fishery sector (scarce natural resource and low substitutability with other production factors) and the fact that demand especially in the Global South will continue to grow.

Figure 21: fishery production trends (% changes over the period 2020-2050)

SSP2-RCP4.5 no lim		SSP2-RCP4.5 10% lim		SSP2-RCP4.5 25% lim		SSP5-RCP8.5 no lim		SSP5-RCP8.5 10% lim	
WestAfrica	230.8	EastAfrica	112.9	WestAfrica	134.9	WestAfrica	441.1	EastAfrica	287.4
EastAfrica	201.7	WestAfrica	108.0	EastAfrica	125.8	EastAfrica	433.3	WestAfrica	148.9
Morocco	141.2	Morocco	56.3	Morocco	80.3	ind	280.0	Senegal	54.7
India	140.6	India	55.8	India	78.1	Morocco	244.5	India	32.2
Senegal	108.0	Senegal	35.9	Senegal	50.2	Senegal	212.1	China	26.1

SSP2-RCP4.5 no lim		SSP2-RCP4.5 10% lim		SSP2-RCP4.5 25% lim		SSP5-RCP8.5 no lim		SSP5-RCP8.5 10% lim	
Ireland	9.3	Ireland	-36.1	Ireland	-25.7	Ireland	24.4	Ireland	-66.4
Norway	16.5	Norway	-27.9	Norway	-17.8	Norway	49.2	Germany	-64.2
Benelux	27.5	New Zel.	-24.5	New Zeland	-12.0	Benelux	50.4	Benelux	-63.1
Germany	28.1	Germany	-23.6	Germany	-10.7	Baltic	57.8	Italy	-62.8
Spain	28.9	Benelux	-22.8	Benelux	-9.8	Germany	58.2	Baltic	-59.9

Table 2: top 5 regions (top) and bottom 5 regions (bottom) by fishery production trends in the five baseline scenarios (% changes over the period 2020-2050)

Baseline scenarios	Cumulative % ch. 2020-50	Average Ann. % ch. 2020-50
SSP2-RCP4.5 no lim	150.9	3.1
SSP2-RCP4.5 10% lim	2901.0	12.0
SSP2-RCP4.5 25% lim	1508.5	9.7
SSP5-RCP8.5 no lim	146.3	3.0
SSP5-RCP8.5 10% lim	13426.3	17.8

Table 3: fish world price trend in the five baseline scenarios

4.3.2 Socio-economic drivers and stressors on Atlantic ecosystem services

4.3.2.1 Introduction

Mapping, evaluating and monitoring of marine ecosystems is essential to enable the identification and consideration of associated ecosystem services in management strategies and policy frameworks. Marine ecosystem services, also referred to as Nature's Contributions to People (NCP) (IPBES 2019) include regulating (e.g. coastal protection), provisioning (e.g. food provision) and cultural services (e.g. tourism and recreation). These services are influenced by multiple, complex socio-economic drivers (e.g. sea temperature rise, fishing, aquaculture, oil production, coastal urbanization, marine tourism). Interactions between drivers create pressures on coastal ecosystems which impact biodiversity, habitat quality, primary production and cultural services (Rocha et al., 2015; Takyi et al., 2023).

Although understanding of how specific anthropogenic drivers impact coastal marine ecosystems and their services has advanced in recent years, such research has focused primarily on single drivers, with less attention paid to multiple driver assessments and their combined effects across spatial and temporal scales (Solé Figueras et al., 2024). Furthermore, inherent biases in research effort towards specific geographic areas (e.g. Europe), marine ecosystems (e.g. coastal), habitat types (e.g. coastal lagoons) and ecosystem service categories (e.g. regulation) as well as disequilibrium in evaluation approaches leaves major gaps in understanding (Addamo et al., 2024). Hence, implementing socio-economic considerations in marine spatial planning is challenging (Stithou, 2017). Effective governance requires adaptability to navigate complex interactions between ecological, economic, social, and institutional components (Villasante et al., 2013).

Several international agreements (e.g. UN Sustainable Development Goals, Global Biodiversity Framework) aim to operationalize marine ecosystem services by facilitating their incorporation into different marine management policies and decision-making processes (e.g. EU Marine Strategy Framework Directive, Marine Spatial Planning Directive), while still allowing for the sustainable exploitation of marine resources (Buonocore et al., 2021). However, there is a need to develop solid evidence at local, national, regional and international scales linking decisions to the anthropogenic impacts on ecosystems and generated services and consequently to human well-being (Buonocore et al., 2021).

The Atlantic Ocean is one such region where understanding the effects of socio-economic drivers is critically important. The combined provisioning, regulating and cultural ecosystem services provided by Atlantic coastal biomes have been conservatively valued at 709.7 billion €/year at 2015 price levels (not including values for urban systems which are typically of highest value) (Filho et al., 2022). The ongoing supply of healthy ecosystem services in the region needs to be weighed against the benefits of economic development and the subsequent costs of ecosystem restoration and well-being of coastal populations. Additionally, it is critical to understand how ecosystem services contribute to human wellbeing and which services are most highly valued by communities in order to prioritise their management. However, there is a significant gap in understanding about the socio-ecological dynamics driving changes to Atlantic ocean ecosystems and associated pressures affecting the supply of ecosystem services. To fill this gap, our research provides an assessment of the state of the art regarding the research on socio-economic drivers and their impacts on Atlantic Ocean ecosystems.

4.3.2.2 Methods for the literature review on socioeconomic drivers on marine ecosystem services

Literature search strategy

We searched for publications in Scopus. To identify relevant publications, we used the search string ("coast* OR ocean OR marine OR island OR sea) AND (Atlantic) AND ("nature contribution*" OR "ecosystem service*") AND

("driver*") AND (PUBYEAR < 2025) on article title, abstract or keyword. Searches included all articles published until our cut-off date of 21 March 2024..

Literature selection criteria

We established five criteria to include publications in our quantitative synthesis. Namely, the publication had (1) to focus on socio-economic drivers and stressors, (2) to mention marine ecosystem services or nature's contributions to people, (3) to focus on any country of the Atlantic Ocean, (4) to be peer-reviewed; and (5) to be written in the English language. We limited the scope of our analysis to publications using the concept of ecosystem services or nature's contributions to people although the first concept is increasingly employed in the understanding, management and governance of natural environments (Hansen et al. 2015). Despite persistent critique, the concept has several strong features, such as revealing and structuring human benefits from nature; creating objects that can be assessed regarding trade-offs and synergies occurring in social-ecological interactions; supporting biodiversity conservation; reconnecting society with natural environments; and linking natural, social sciences, and humanities (Schröter et al. 2014).

Literature review process

Our systematic review followed the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) statement (Moher 2009). The PRISMA checklist of items is reported to enhance the transparency and robustness of the review process. Following the PRISMA, we divided the systematic review into four phases (Figure 1). First, we identified 63 potentially relevant records of which we screened all titles and abstracts. Second, we read through full-texts to examine whether publications were eligible for our final quantitative synthesis of which 13 failed to meet our inclusion criteria. Finally, we carried out a quantitative synthesis of 50 publications.

Figure 22. Literature review flow diagram. The literature review followed the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) (Moher 2009).

Before starting the data collection, we carried out a 'calibration' exercise to attain a uniform data collection procedure among co-authors. This consisted of reviewing a randomly selected publication that had been previously identified for quantitative synthesis. Each co-author assessed this publication individually and subsequently the

results were compared against each other. The outcome of the exercise resulted in our template for the data collection process.

Data collection

The systematic review data included 14 variables and their corresponding response categories (Table 4).

Table 4. Data variables and corresponding categories used to collect data in the literature review

Data variables	Categories
Year of publication	e.g. 2021, 2022
Country of case study	e.g. Argentina, Brazil, Spain
Type of document	e.g. article, conference, report
Main discipline	e.g. environmental, economic, social, mixed
Type of paper	e.g. conceptual, empirical, review
Type of method	e.g. field experiment, surveys
Source of information	e.g. time series, models
Type of ecosystem	e.g. marine, coastal, ocean
Habitat type	e.g. coral reefs, mangroves, seagrass meadow
Direct drivers of change affecting ES or NCP	e.g. overfishing, pollution, invasive species, climate change
Indirect drivers of change affecting ES or NCP	e.g. economic, demographic, technological, governance
Does the study link with Nature’s Contributions to People	Yes, No
Does the study link to spatial planning?	Yes, No
Does the study link to human wellbeing?	Yes, No

4.3.2.3 Results

Main patterns and key concepts in the record titles

The dataset spans from the earliest publication in 2004 (Wainger & Price, 2004) to the most recent publications in 2024 (Brito et al., 2024; Benjamin et al., 2024; El Behja et al., 2024; Saulinier et al., 2024). On average, publications are distributed across several years, with some clustering around 2017-2021. The highest number of citations is 295, found in Mason et al. (2014), while the lowest is 0 citations, seen in recent papers (Brito et al., 2024; Benjamin et al., 2024; Saulinier et al., 2024). Empirical studies comprise 70% of the dataset, emphasizing field experiments, database analyses, and statistical modeling.

From a visual point of view, this academic literature generates a valuable contribution with the development of key concepts. Figure 23 shows, by way of example, how an interconnection from high to low importance the words and frequency is developed in the titles of the study sample whereby the larger the size of the word indicates the greater frequency with which it was mentioned (Bauerdorf et al., 2020; Hossain et al., 2021; Seijo et al., 2022; Villasante & Seijo, 2023).

The concept cloud reflects the most frequently used words in the title of the literature analysed. The central term, "driver," refers to the elements that drive changes in these ecosystems, such as climate change, fishing, and pollution. In this context, "ecosystem" highlights the importance of marine and coastal systems, which are constantly interacting with various drivers (Brito et al., 2024; Möllmann et al., 2012; Roik et al., 2016; Pauly et al., 2017).

The concept of "community" suggests that the changes driven by these factors affect both biological and human communities, including fisheries and coastal populations. Likewise, the term "impact" indicates that drivers generate measurable effects on ecosystems and societies, such as biodiversity loss and alterations in ecosystem services. In response to these changes, the concept of "management" underscores the importance of strategies to mitigate the negative effects of these factors (Smith et al., 2023; McGarrigle et al., 2024; Manson et al., 2014; Tagliabue et al., 2021; Ojaveer et al. 2021; van et al., 2019; Garwood et al., 2023).

The frequency with which the term "climate" is mentioned demonstrates that climate change is one of the main drivers in the Atlantic, affecting temperature, ocean acidification, and circulation patterns. The notion of "resilience" highlights the capacity of ecosystems and communities to adapt to or recover from these impacts. In this regard, biodiversity, represented by words like "species," is directly affected by these changes, which can alter the distribution and abundance of marine organisms (Armstrong et al. , 2019; Bernal et al., 2021; Saulnier et al., 2023).

Figure 23. Key concepts mentioned in the record titles (N=50).

Additionally, the presence of "reef" in the concept cloud refers to key ecosystems, such as coral reefs, which are particularly sensitive to environmental changes and human activities. On the other hand, the word "spill" suggests the occurrence of pollution events, such as oil spills, which can have adverse effects on marine life and water quality (Adam et al., 2015; Ferreira et al., 2019; Manson et al., 2014; Smith et al., 2023; Tatariw et al., 2018).

Therefore, the drivers affecting the Atlantic include both natural and anthropogenic factors, such as climate change, pollution, and habitat degradation (Filho et al. 2022). The interaction between these factors and marine ecosystems highlights the need for effective management to minimize negative impacts and strengthen the resilience of ecological systems and human communities that depend on them (Armstrong et al., 2019; Ashford et al., 2019; Brandini et al., 2018; Bridges et al., 2021; Lins et al., 2021; Takyi et al., 2023; Teixeira et al., 2021).

Types of studies, methods, sources of information

Figure 24 shows the distribution of study types, indicating a clear predominance of empirical studies (70%), indicating that conducting fieldwork to gather primary data is a scientific priority. This is followed by literature reviews (17%), suggesting an interest in synthesizing existing knowledge. In contrast, conceptual, descriptive, and meta-analysis studies have minimal representation (2-4%), highlighting a lower production of theoretical or exploratory studies compared to those based on empirical evidence.

Figure 24. Types of studies of publications analysed (%) (N=50).

Figure 25 presents the data collection methods employed, highlighting the predominance of database usage (32%), field experiments (25%), and scientific articles (22%) as the primary sources. These findings indicate a strong emphasis on the gathering of structured data and empirical evidence. To a lesser extent, methods such as referring to grey literature (7%), expert panels (6%), and surveys or participatory workshops (3% each) are also utilized, suggesting a complementary use of both qualitative and quantitative approaches. Use of laboratory experiments (3%), reflects the diversity of strategies for information acquisition, albeit with lower representation in this context.

Figure 25. Type of methods used in the publications analysed (in %) (N=50).

Figure 26 illustrates an emphasis on quantitative data analysis approaches employed across the studies, demonstrating frequent use of statistical analysis (36%) models (24%) and time series analysis (12%). Use of quantitative (16%) and qualitative data was mentioned less frequently (10%), but suggest the adoption of mixed-methods approaches.

Figure 26. Sources of information used in the publications analysed (in %) (N=50).

Type of ecosystems

The studies analysed were conducted in ecosystems around the Atlantic Ocean but were more prevalent on the North American (20 records), European (14) and West African (10) continents (Table 2). Five studies were conducted on the South American continent, mostly within the last few years. One study was conducted across the Atlantic in the open ocean.

Most studies (74%) focused on individual types of ecosystems, including:

- coastal areas intensively used for multiple purposes by humans (10 records) (Wainger & Price 2004; Alvarez-Filip et al. 2011; Möllmann & Diekmann 2012; Lefcheck et al. 2017; Howarth et al. 2018; Brandini 2018; Bridges et al. 2021; Takyi et al. 2023; McGarrigle et al. 2024; Brito et al. 2024.);
- shelf ecosystems (neritic and intertidal/littoral zone) (9) (Mason et al. 2014; Tatariw et al. 2018; Bonino et al. 2019; Staudinger et al. 2020; Tagliabue et al. 2021; Hyytiäinen et al. 2021; van Regteren et al. 2022; Saulnier et al. 2023; Valdazo et al. 2024);
- marine areas (mangroves, coral reefs etc.) (8) (Ballé-Béganton et al. 2012; Adam et al. 2015; Derouen et al. 2020; El Mahrad et al. 2020; Friedland et al. 2021; Carruthers et al. 2022; Garwood et al. 2023; El Behja et al. 2024);
- deep-sea (7) (Ashford et al. 2019; Franz et al. 2019; Puerta et al. 2020; Fonseca et al. 2021; Teixeira et al. 2021; Smith & Castorani 2023; Volety et al. 2024);
- open ocean pelagic systems (euphotic zone) (2) (Altman et al. 2011; Ojaveer et al. 2023); and
- coastal saltmarsh (1) (Armstrong et al. 2019).

One fifth of records (22%) studied two types of ecosystem, including:

- coastal areas intensively used for multiple purposes by humans and marine areas (mangroves, coral reefs etc.) (5) (Sambe et al. 2016; Smale & Moore 2017; García-Alonso et al. 2019; Weaver & Armitage 2020; Neves et al. 2021);
- high sea and deep sea (1) (Benjamin et al. 2024);
- coastal areas intensively used for multiple purposes by humans and inland surface waters and water bodies/freshwater (1) (Havenhand et al. 2019);
- coastal areas intensively used for multiple purposes by humans and coastal wetlands (1) (Gabler et al. 2017);
- coastal areas intensively used for multiple purposes by humans and open ocean pelagic systems (euphotic zone) (1) (Randazzo-Eisemann & Garza-Pérez 2023);
- shelf ecosystems (neritic and intertidal/littoral zone) and wetlands – fens, mires, bogs (1) (Soares et al. 2022)
- shelf ecosystems (neritic and intertidal/littoral zone) and marine areas (mangroves, coral reefs etc.) (1) (Norkko et al. 2012);

A small proportion of records (4%) studied three or four types of ecosystem:

- coastal areas intensively used for multiple purposes by humans and open ocean pelagic systems (euphotic zone) and high sea (1) (Pauly 2007).
- coastal areas intensively used for multiple purposes by humans, shelf ecosystems (neritic and intertidal/littoral zone), open ocean pelagic systems (euphotic zone) and marine areas (mangroves, coral reefs etc.) (1) (Kirkman et al. 2016).

Table 5. Summary of the ecosystems studied according to continent and type of ecosystem.

Continent	Nº of records	Names of ecosystems studied	Nº of ecosystem types studied	Types of ecosystems studied	References
North America	20	Alacranes Reef, Apalachicola River and Estuary, Aransas Bay and Corpus Christi Bay, Bay of Fundy and Southern Gulf of St Lawrence, Eastern Scotian Shelf, Flemish Cap and Grand Banks, Flemish Pass, Gulf of Maine, Louisiana, Louisiana, Middle Atlantic Bight, Mid-Atlantic Region, Northern Gulf of Mexico, Northern Gulf of Mexico Coast, Northwest Atlantic Ocean, South Bay and Chincoteague Bay, Southwest Florida shelf, Southwest Atlantic, The Chandeleur Islands, United States Gulf and Atlantic coasts, Wider Caribbean basin	6	Coastal areas intensively used for multiple purposes by humans, Coastal salt marsh, Deep-Sea, Marine areas (mangroves, coral reefs etc.), Open ocean pelagic systems (euphotic zone), Shelf ecosystems (neritic and intertidal/littoral zone).	Adam et al. 2015, Altman et al. 2011, Alvarez-Filip et al. 2011, Ashford et al. 2019, Carruthers et al. 2022, Derouen et al. 2020, Friedland et al. 2021, Gabler et al. 2017, Garwood et al. 2023, Lefcheck et al. 2017, Mason et al. 2014, McGarrigle et al. 2024, Möllmann & Diekmann 2012, Randazzo-Eisemann & Garza-Pérez 2023, Smith & Castorani 2023, Staudinger et al. 2020, Tatariw et al. 2018, Voley et al. 2024, Wainger & Price 2004, Weaver & Armitage 2020.
Europe	14	Ascension Island, Baltic Sea, Baltic-Skagerrak System (Baltic Sea), Bay of Biscay, Charente River watershed, Celtic Sea and English Channel, English Channel, Ireland Sea, Kiel Bay and Lubeck Bay (South West Baltic Sea), North Atlantic Ocean (deep sea), Northern Baltic Sea, Pertuis Charentais Sea, Scotland, Saint Helena and Tristan da Cunha (seamounts and oceanic islands), Wales, Westhoek	6	Coastal areas intensively used for multiple purposes by humans, Coastal salt marsh, Deep-Sea, Inland surface waters and water bodies/freshwater, Marine areas (mangroves, coral reefs etc.), Shelf ecosystems (neritic and intertidal/littoral zone).	Armstrong et al. 2019, Ballé-Béganton et al. 2012, Benjamin et al. 2024, Bridges et al. 2021, Franz et al. 2019, Havenhand et al. 2019, Howarth et al. 2018, Hyytiäinen et al. 2021, Norkko et al. 2012, Ojaveer et al. 2023, Puerta et al. 2020, Saulnier et al. 2023, Smale & Moore 2017, van Regteren et al. 2022.
West Africa	10	Benguela Current, Benguela Current System, Canary Current Large Marine Ecosystem, Gran Canaria, Khenifiss, Khenifiss Lagoon, Moulay Boussselham, North Atlantic, Sidi Moussa, The Azores.	5	Coastal areas intensively used for multiple purposes by humans, High sea, Marine areas (mangroves, coral reefs etc.), Open ocean pelagic systems (euphotic zone), Shelf ecosystems (neritic and intertidal/littoral zone).	Bonino et al. 2019, Brito et al. 2024, El Behja et al. 2024, El Mahrad et al. 2020, Kirkman et al. 2016, Neves et al. 2021, Pauly 2007, Sambe et al. 2016, Takyi et al. 2023, Valdazo et al. 2024.
South America	5	Abrolhos reefs, Bay of Santa Catarina Island, Río de la Plata basin, South Atlantic Ocean, Southwest Atlantic	4	Coastal areas intensively used for multiple purposes by humans, Deep-Sea, Marine areas (mangroves, coral reefs etc.), Wetlands – fens, mires, bogs.	Brandini 2018, Fonseca et al. 2021, García-Alonso et al. 2019, Soares et al. 2022, Teixeira et al. 2021.
Atlantic	1	Atlantic sub-polar, North Atlantic sub-tropical gyre,	1	Open ocean pelagic systems (euphotic zone)	Tagliabue et al. 2021

		Equatorial Atlantic, South Atlantic sub-tropical gyre		
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Drivers of marine ecosystem services

Climate change was identified as a very important driver in 28% of records, followed by change in land use (10%), pollution (6%), use of the sea (6%) and invasive species (4%).

When analyzing the actors linked to direct ecosystem drivers (Figure 27), the majority of records (30%) did not mention specific actors. The records that did mention actors identified a wide range from different industry sectors. Fishers accounted for 6% of interactions identified between actors and drivers, reflecting their direct dependence on the marine ecosystem (Volety et al., 2014).

Where records did link actors to direct drivers, land use change linked to the agriculture sector was among the most frequently cited (6%), reflecting the recognition of agricultural activities as a key driver of changes to the marine environment. Similarly, local communities (6%) and NGOs (5%) were mentioned in relation to pollution and resource use (Benjamin et al., 2024). Public administrations (5%) and the private sector (5%) were mentioned in relation to regulation and resource exploitation (Gabler et al, 2017; Volety et al., 2014). Meanwhile, other private or public actors such as financial institutions, renewable industries, and unions, appear less mentioned in the documents.

Additionally, some documents mention interactions between multiple drivers, such as land use change and pollution (4%), and land use change combined with resource exploitation (2%) (Wainger & Price, 2004). For other significant drivers, including climate change, invasive species (Norkko et al., 2012) and pollution, actors are scarcely mentioned, each accounting for less than 2% of responses. This pattern suggests that while some documents acknowledge key drivers of environmental change, they did not typically link them to specific actors.

Figure 27. Correlations between actors and direct socioeconomic drivers (N=50).

Types of Nature’s Contributions to People (NCP)

Overall, records most frequently mentioned material services (11% of responses) compared with regulation (5%) or non-material (1%) regarding types of NCP. Most responses (84%) did not mention any type of service.

Among the types of NCP reported in the records analysed (Figure 28), ‘creation and maintenance of habitats’ was mentioned most frequently (63% of records) and was associated most often with regulation (37%) and material (25%) services. ‘Regulation of freshwater and coastal water quality’ (54%) was mostly associated with material (44%) services. Similarly ‘food and feed’ (40%) was most frequently associated with material (38%) services. Types of NCP that were least frequently mentioned in the records include: ‘pollinization and dispersal of seeds and other propagules’, ‘regulation of air quality’ and ‘medicinal, biochemical and genetic resources’ each being mentioned in only 2% of records, indicating significant knowledge gaps in the literature analysed.

The emphasis of scientific effort on material services associated with contributions of water and habitat quality, and food and feed to people suggests these three types of NCP may be inter-linked and is indicative of their importance to human wellbeing. This finding supports the overall research bias we identified towards coastal areas in the literature regarding socio-economic drivers and stressors on marine ecosystem services, while broader ecological and societal interdependencies have been overlooked to date.

Material	Non-material	Regulation	Not mentioned	Contribution
25	2	37	37	Creation and maintenance of habitats
2	0	0	98	Pollinization and dispersal of seeds and other propagules
2	0	0	98	Regulation of air quality
12	2	20	66	Regulation of climate
2	0	8	90	Regulation of ocean acidification
10	2	2	90	Regulation of the quantity, location and availability of fresh water
45	4	6	47	Regulation of freshwater and coastal water quality
4	2	0	94	Formation, protection and decontamination of soils and sediments
6	0	4	90	Regulation of hazards and extreme events
10	2	0	88	Regulation of harmful organisms and biological processes
10	0	2	88	Energy
38	0	2	60	Food and feed
8	0	0	92	Materials, companionship and labour
2	0	0	98	Medicinal, biochemical and genetic resources
2	2	0	96	Learning and inspiration
2	4	0	94	Physical and psychological experiences
2	4	0	94	Supporting identities / sense of belonging
8	2	2	89	Maintaining choices

Figure 28. Nature Contributions to People mentioned in the review (in %) (N=50).

Spatial planning and indicators

Figure 29 presents varying levels of association with the 11 indicators evaluated under the European Union Marine Strategy Framework Directive. The results are categorized into three groups: high values ($\geq 70\%$), medium values (30%–69%), and low values ($<30\%$), facilitating a clearer interpretation of the availability of studies aligned with the European strategic framework (European Parliament and Council of the European Union, 2008).

High values indicate a strong association with the evaluated indicators in the literature. Notably, marine food webs display a 50% association, highlighting a growing interest in the study of ecosystem food structures. Indicators classified within the medium-value range exhibit a balanced distribution or a moderate tendency. Eutrophication (36%) and the alteration of hydrographic conditions (32%) are relatively of medium presence in the literature, indicating a limited attention to environmental pressures affecting marine water quality. Likewise, the presence of water contaminants is reported at 34%, leading to potential gaps in the identification of anthropogenic pollution sources. Similarly, the presence of commercial species stands at 30%, reflecting a medium interest in the sustainable management of fisheries resources.

Figure 29. Indicators mentioned in the review (in %) (N=50).

Conversely, low values correspond to critical environmental factors that receive minimal attention in the reviewed literature. Seabed integrity is documented at 12%, suggesting limited research on benthic habitat disturbances. The presence of indigenous species is recorded at 16%, underscoring challenges in the conservation of native biodiversity. Contamination in fish and shellfish for human consumption exhibits the lowest association (8%), implying a lack of emphasis on food safety concerns. Additionally, marine litter, biological diversity and the introduction of energy, including underwater noise, are similarly low at 10%. These findings underscore both progress and persisting challenges in marine environmental management, showing that while certain indicators exhibit strong research alignment, others remain underrepresented.

Indicators related to human well-being

Most documents did not mention a link between ecosystems and human well-being (Figure 30). Across the majority of well-being categories, responses overwhelmingly indicate “No”, emphasizing the focus on the natural sciences in the literature analysed.

Figure 30. Categories of indicators of human well-being mentioned in the review (in %) (N=50).

Food access was the most frequently mentioned (52%), highlighting the importance of food security in relation to ecosystem and human wellbeing. The lack of recognition of housing, health, and equity-related contributions further reinforces the idea that ecosystem services are often framed narrowly in terms of economic or resource-based benefits.

The Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) and the Ocean Health Index (OHI) share common objectives aimed at preserving marine ecosystem health, with a strong focus on biodiversity. The MSFD descriptors consistently highlight biodiversity, particularly in relation to the conservation of marine species and habitats. For example, Descriptor 1 emphasizes biodiversity conservation, directly aligning with the OHI biodiversity goal, while descriptor 2 addresses the impacts of non-indigenous species for the same goal. Descriptors 3 and 4 support OHI’s fisheries and biodiversity goals. Descriptors 5, 6, 8, and 10, which address eutrophication, seabed integrity, contaminants, and marine litter, link with the OHI clean waters, carbon storage, and tourism goals, all of which are essential for monitoring ecosystems. Descriptors 7, 9, and 11, related to environmental conditions, and seafood safety, align with the OHI coastal protection, food provision, and biodiversity goals. Rooted in the UN Sustainable Development Goals for 2030, both frameworks offer an integrated approach for managing and monitoring marine ecosystems, ensuring progress toward the 2030 UN agenda.

4.3.2.4 Summary

A general framework to identify trends regarding conceptualization of the services provided by marine ecosystems has been explored through a systematic review of the scientific literature on socio-economic drivers and stressors, drawing on peer-reviewed and quality-indexed academic publications. Categorized impacts (e.g. pressures, drivers, stressors, threats, opportunities, benefits) and social transformations have been identified according to IPBES indirect and direct drivers of biodiversity and ecosystem change.

The main findings of our review indicate that the investigation of socio-economic drivers on marine ecosystem services in the Atlantic Ocean is an emerging field and is strongly focused on empirical data gathering through

natural scientific research. Most research investigated individual types of ecosystems situated along the coastlines of the North American, European and West African continents, including intensively used coastal areas, shelf ecosystems and marine areas such as coral reefs highlighting the perceived importance of these areas and ecosystems to scientists working in the field. Furthermore, regulating and material services emerged as most frequently cited. These findings correspond with the finding that climate change and change in land use were identified as very important socio-economic drivers since their effects are most likely to be noticed in ecosystems which are most sensitive to associated impacts, and which are of material importance to human societies. Despite this, social science studies exploring the links between socio-economic drivers and their effects on marine ecosystem services were lacking in our review and represent a significant gap in knowledge as well as an opportunity for increasing relevant understanding.

5 Conclusions

Contribution to the overall AtlantECO objectives:

We have contributed extensively to the overall AtlantECO objectives, especially to the objective OBJ3 “Assess drivers and stressors of change in the Atlantic Ocean”. The results summarized in the present deliverable have opened new research opportunities and conceptual frameworks that represent an important legacy of the project.

Impact and progress beyond state-of-the-art:

The work carried out to identify the main drivers of change from observation-based data led to significant advancements by transitioning from purely statistical techniques to physically grounded empirical stochastic models. The inclusion of multiple variables representative of the most relevant upper ocean processes and their time derivatives in the state vector represents by itself a relevant conceptual advance for empirical climate modelling, offering a more comprehensive representation of ocean dynamics. By further introducing a dynamical geography of seascape changes that takes advantage of machine learning techniques, we successfully identified the global and local physical drivers responsible for the observed trends in chlorophyll concentration, moving beyond the traditional focus on temperature-induced stratification changes alone. This provides a more comprehensive understanding of the mechanisms influencing phytoplankton abundance.

For the first time, direct observation-based estimates of organic carbon export have been obtained from data-driven time series, allowing to describe interannual signals that could not be detected starting from climatological fields or assuming steady-state solutions as those obtained from data-constrained ocean circulation inverse models. While still representing a prototypical approach, this work lays the foundation for a scientifically sound exploitation of state-of-the-art reconstruction of the ocean state based on machine/deep learning techniques.

Lessons learnt and links built:

The multivariate empirical stochastic modelling approach may serve as a “higher-order” benchmark for validating numerical climate models. Moreover, it provides a foundation for exploring the impacts of climate change on marine ecosystems, such as by comparing our dynamical regimes with recently discovered plankton genomic biogeographies (Fremont et al., 2022). This knowledge can also inform more effective ocean monitoring strategies and efforts to preserve marine ecosystems.

Socio-economic analyses and perspectives:

The main findings of the literature review indicate that the investigation of socio-economic drivers on marine ecosystem services in the Atlantic Ocean is an emerging field, and is strongly focused on empirical data gathering through natural scientific research. Most research investigated individual types of ecosystems situated along the coastlines of the North American, European and West African continents, including intensively used coastal areas, shelf ecosystems and marine areas such as coral reefs highlighting the perceived importance of these areas and ecosystems to scientists working in the field. Furthermore, regulating and material services emerged as most frequently cited. These findings correspond with the finding that climate change and change in land use were identified as very important socio-economic drivers since their effects are most likely to be noticed in ecosystems

which are most sensitive to associated impacts and which are of material importance to human societies. Despite this, social science studies exploring the links between socio-economic drivers and their effects on marine ecosystem services were lacking in our review and represent a significant gap in knowledge as well as an opportunity for increasing relevant understanding.

6 References

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7 Annexes

Section 4.3. Socio-economic drivers and stressors on Atlantic ecosystem services

Questionnaire to analyze socioeconomic drivers and stressors on marine ecosystem services in the Atlantic Ocean

Q0. Coder_

- Q1. Case N°_
- Q2. Document title_
- Q3. Year of publication_
- Q4. No. of citations
- Q5. Type of document
- Article_
 - Conference_
 - Book Chapter_
 - Book_
 - Other:_
- Q6. Discipline of the document
- Natural Sciences_
 - Social Sciences_
 - Mixed_
- Q7. Countries of the Atlantic referred to in the text
- Q8. Type of ecosystem where the study was conducted *
- Coast_
 - Ocean_
 - Marine_
 - Island_
 - Sea_
 - Other:_
- Q9. Type of marine ecosystem referred to in the text (IPBES 2019)
- Wetlands – fens, mires, bogs_
 - Permafrost/glacial habitats_
 - Inland surface waters and water bodies/freshwater_
 - Shelf ecosystems (neritic and intertidal/littoral zone)_
 - Open ocean pelagic systems (euphotic zone)_
 - High sea_
 - Deep-Sea_
 - Coastal areas intensively used for multiple purposes by humans_
 - Marine areas (mangroves, coral reefs etc.)_
 - Other:
- Q10. Conceptual framework for the case study (Atlantic)
- nature contribution_
 - ecosystem service_
 - Both_
 - Other:_
- Q11. Type of study referenced in the document
- Conceptual_
 - Descriptive_
 - Empirical_
 - Review_
 - Editorial_
 - Opinion_
 - Meta-analysis_
 - Other:_
- Q12. Data collection

- Field experiment_
- Expert panel_
- Survey / questionnaire_
- Participatory workshop_
- Data base_
- Gray literature_
- Scientific article_
- Other:_

Q13. Data analysis

- Models_
- Time Series_
- Quantitative data/information_
- Qualitative data/information_
- Statistical analysis_
- Other:_

Q14. Species are mentioned in the document

- Yes_
- No_
- Other:_

Q15. If any species are identified in the document, please indicate the scientific name(s) of the species *Identify the name of the scientific species.

Q16. Which main type of driver is contemplated in the case study according to the following options (select those that apply)?

- Pressure_
- Driver_
- Opportunity_
- Benefit_
- Threat_
- Impact_
- Barrier_
- Risk_
- Other:_

Q17. Direct driver on the ecosystem. Include up to a maximum of three (if necessary) and order them by importance according to the author (1= Highly important, 2= Moderately important, 3= Slightly important) (IPBES, 2019).

Direct Driver	Very Important	Medium important	Slightly important	Not mentioned
Land use change				
Sea use				
Climate Change				
Pollution-Pollution				

Use and exploitation of natural resources				
Invasive species				
Other:				

Q18. Other direct ecosystem driver(s).

Q19a. Which actor/s are most linked to direct ecosystem drivers in the document?

Actor/s	Land use change	Sea use	Climate Change	Pollution	Use and exploitation of natural resources	Invasive species	Other
Fisher							
Shellfish harvester							
Commercial fisher							
Tourism							
NGO's							
Local Community							
Ports							
Scientific community							
Government							
Recreational fishermen							
Non-renewable industry							
Private sector							
Public Administration							
Agriculture							
Forestry Sector							
Citizens							
Indigenous community							
Social movements							
Trade unions							
Shipping companies							
Financial Institutions							

Renewable industry							
Others							
Not mentioned							

Q19b. Other direct actor(s) and/or driver(s) affecting the ecosystem(s)*.

Q20a. Select three indirect drivers on marine ecosystem indicated in the document. Order the list of indirect drivers as: 1 = primary, 2 = secondary, 3 = tertiary. If no indirect driver is mentioned, state it explicitly. (IPBES, 2019)

Indirect drivers	Demographic	Economic	Governance	Values	Technological	Not mentioned
Main						
Secondary						
Tertiary						
Other						
Not Mentioned						

Q20b. Other indirect drivers mentioned in the document

Q21a. Which actor/s are most linked to the indirect drivers?

Actor/s	Land use change	Sea use	Climate Change	Pollution	Use and exploitation of natural resources	Invasive species	Other
Fisher							
Shellfish harvester							
Commercial fisher							
Tourism							
NGO's							
Local Community							
Ports							
Scientific community							
Government							
Recreational fishermen							
Non-renewable industry							
Private sector							
Public Administration							
Agriculture							
Forestry Sector							

Citizens							
Indigenous community							
Social movements							
Trade unions							
Shipping companies							
Financial Institutions							
Renewable industry							
Others							
Not mentioned							

Q21b. Other actors interacting with indirect drivers

Q22. Effect on transformative change. Choose one or all three or others considered in the document.

	Practices: Practices refer to what we do, and can include the behaviors and actions of people both individually and collectively. Practices can mean actions, habits and routines, decisions and experiments, and innovations. They include the ways in which people collectively create and interact with social innovations as a way of adapting to change and the use and adoption of technology.
	Values / Beliefs: Views refer to how we see the world and our place in it, as well as what we value and prioritize. Throughout the literature, reference is made to views, values, worldviews, opinions, motivations, creativity and visions.
	Institutions / structures: Institutions/structures include, for example, laws, institutions, rules, policies, regulatory frameworks, organizations, etc. They encompass the categories we usually think of as organizational forms (at the legal level), e.g., notions of the state, institutions, laws and rules (including the rules of conservation and extractive regimes), norms, concepts and discourses (including rights, justice, freedom, private property, individual responsibility, nature and culture).
	Other:

Q23. Primary focus of the study (choose one)

Indirect drivers	Mentioned (Yes/No)
Environmental	
Social	
Economic	
Governance	
Other: _	

Q23.a. Justify the main focus with a short sentence.

Q24. Does the proposed case have an ecosystem approach in the document? Yes_ No_

Q25. Indicates if the document explicitly mentions any type of the Contributions to Nature (Diaz et al. 2018)

Type of Nature's Contributions to People	Material	Non-material	Regulation
Creation and maintenance of habitats			
Pollinization and dispersal of seeds and other propagules			
Air quality regulation			
Climate regulation			
Regulation of ocean acidification			
Regulation of the quantity, location and availability of fresh water			
Regulation of freshwater and coastal water quality			
Formation, protection and decontamination of soils and sediments			
Regulation of hazards and extreme events			
Regulation of harmful organisms and biological processes.			
Energy			
Food and feed			
Materials, companionship and labor			
Medicinal, biochemical and genetic resources.			
Learning and inspiration.			
Physical and psychological experiences			
Supporting identities/sense of belonging			
Maintaining choices			

Q26. Indicate if the document mentions any of the following aspects of human well-being

Human well-being	Mentioned (Yes/No)
Quality employment	
Income-wage	
Population fixation	
Human health	

Tourism	
Cultural identity	
Food access	
Water	
Housing	
Education	
Good social relations	
Physical, energy and livelihood security	
Equity	
Material prosperity	
Spiritual satisfaction	
Freedom of choice	
Action and participation in society	
Other	

Q27. Which other aspects the study refer to human well-being. Specify_

Q28. Indicate if the document refers to marine spatial planning: Yes_ No_

Q29. If Yes, please specify the name of the planning instrument:

Q30. Indicate if the document refers to the following categories of the EU Marine Strategy Framework Directive

Categories	Mentioned (Yes/No)
Biological diversity	
Non-indigenous species	
Commercial species	
Marine foodwebs	
Eutrophication	
Sea floor integrity	
Alteration of hydrographical conditions	
Contaminants	
Contaminants in fish and seafood for human consumption	
Marine litter	
Introduction of energy, including underwater noise	

Q31. Indicate if the study addresses any of the 10 Goals of the Ocean Health Index.

Clean waters_

Nature's products_

Coastal Protection_

Artisanal fishing opportunities_

Biodiversity_

Carbon storage_

Livelihoods and Economy_

Food provisioning_

Sense of place_

Tourism and recreation_

Q32. Indicate if the document refers to future scenarios or pathways: Yes_ No_.

Q33. If the answer of Q32 is Yes, please indicate the name of the scenario (IPCC, models, denomination)

Q34. Other relevant comments

Table S1. List of papers included in the literature review

Title	Year	Journal	DOI
Metagenomics reveals sediment microbial community response to Deepwater Horizon oil spill	2014	ISME Journal	10.1038/ismej.2013.254
Macroclimatic change expected to transform coastal wetland ecosystems this century	2017	Nature Climate Change	10.1038/nclimate3203
A welcome can of worms? Hypoxia mitigation by an invasive species	2012	Global Change Biology	10.1111/j.1365-2486.2011.02513.x
Herbivory and the resilience of Caribbean coral reefs: Knowledge gaps and implications for management	2015	Marine Ecology Progress Series	10.3354/meps11170
Marine Ecosystem Regime Shifts Induced by Climate and Overfishing. A Review for the Northern Hemisphere	2012	Advances in Ecological Research	10.1016/B978-0-12-398315-2.00004-1
Monitoring of wetland inundation dynamics in the Delmarva Peninsula using Landsat time-series imagery from 1985 to 2011	2017	Remote Sensing of Environment	10.1016/j.rse.2016.12.001
The sea around us project: Documenting and communicating global fisheries impacts on marine ecosystems	2007	Ambio	10.1579/0044-7447(2007)36[290:TSAUPD]2.0.CO;2
Wish you were here: How defaunated is the Atlantic Forest biome of its medium- to large-bodied mammal fauna?	2019	PLoS ONE	10.1371/journal.pone.0204515
Persistent Uncertainties in Ocean Net Primary Production Climate Change Projections at Regional Scales Raise Challenges for Assessing Impacts on Ecosystem Services	2021	Frontiers in Climate	10.3389/fclim.2021.738224
Drivers of region-wide declines in architectural complexity on Caribbean reefs	2011	Coral Reefs	10.1007/s00338-011-0795-6
Social-Environmental Analysis for the Management of Coastal Lagoons in North Africa	2020	Frontiers in Environmental Science	10.3389/fenvs.2020.00037
Influence of Water Masses on the Biodiversity and Biogeography of Deep-Sea Benthic Ecosystems in the North Atlantic	2020	Frontiers in Marine Science	10.3389/fmars.2020.00239
Variability in kelp forest structure along a latitudinal gradient in ocean temperature	2017	Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology	10.1016/j.jembe.2016.10.023
Interannual to decadal variability within and across the major Eastern Boundary Upwelling Systems	2019	Scientific Reports	10.1038/s41598-019-56514-8
The role of sand lances (<i>Ammodytes</i> sp.) in the Northwest Atlantic Ecosystem: A synthesis of current knowledge with implications for conservation and management	2020	Fish and Fisheries	10.1111/faf.12445
Spatial characterisation of the Benguela ecosystem for ecosystem-based management	2016	African Journal of Marine Science	10.2989/1814232X.2015.1125390
Ecological condition and value of oyster reefs of the Southwest Florida shelf ecosystem	2014	Ecological Indicators	10.1016/j.ecolind.2014.03.012
Structural equation modeling approach to the diversity-productivity relationship of Wadden Sea phytoplankton	2015	Marine Ecology Progress Series	10.3354/meps11153
A practical approach to implementation of ecosystem-based management: A case study using the Gulf of Maine marine ecosystem	2011	Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment	10.1890/080186
Rewilding defaunated Atlantic Forests with tortoises to restore lost seed dispersal functions	2017	Perspectives in Ecology and Conservation	10.1016/j.pecon.2017.08.005

Restored Eelgrass (<i>Zostera marina</i> L.) as a Refuge for Epifaunal Biodiversity in Mid-Western Atlantic Coastal Bays	2017	Estuaries and Coasts	10.1007/s12237-016-0141-x
Disentangling the relative role of climate change on tree growth in an extreme Mediterranean environment	2018	Science of the Total Environment	10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.06.064
Hydroclimatic controls on non-stationary stream water ages in humid tropical catchments	2016	Journal of Hydrology	10.1016/j.jhydrol.2016.09.006
Variations in productivity of the Canary Current Large Marine Ecosystem and their effects on small pelagic fish stocks	2016	Environmental Development	10.1016/j.envdev.2015.11.012
Coral reef carbonate budgets and ecological drivers in the central Red Sea - A naturally high temperature and high total alkalinity environment	2018	Biogeosciences	10.5194/bg-15-6277-2018
Expert assessment of risks posed by climate change and anthropogenic activities to ecosystem services in the deep North Atlantic	2019	Frontiers in Marine Science	10.3389/fmars.2019.00158
Patterns and drivers of understory macroalgal assemblage structure within subtidal kelp forests	2020	Biodiversity and Conservation	10.1007/s10531-020-02070-x
Río de la Plata: A Neotropical Estuarine System	2019	Coasts and Estuaries: The Future	10.1016/B978-0-12-814003-1.00003-4
Benthic Assemblage Composition of South Atlantic Seamounts	2021	Frontiers in Marine Science	10.3389/fmars.2021.660648
Decadal (2006-2018) dynamics of Southwestern Atlantic's largest turbid zone reefs	2021	PLoS ONE	10.1371/journal.pone.0247111
Provision of aquatic ecosystem services as a consequence of societal changes: The case of the Baltic Sea	2021	Population Ecology	10.1002/1438-390X.12033
Meta-analysis on the ecological impacts of widely spread non-indigenous species in the Baltic Sea	2021	Science of the Total Environment	10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.147375
The North-Eastern Atlantic Forest: Biogeographical, historical, and current aspects in the sugarcane zone	2021	The Atlantic Forest: History, Biodiversity, Threats and Opportunities of the Mega-diverse Forest	10.1007/978-3-030-55322-7_3
Investigating the environmental drivers of deep-seafloor biodiversity: A case study of peracarid crustacean assemblages in the Northwest Atlantic Ocean	2019	Ecology and Evolution	10.1002/ece3.5852
Ecological and functional consequences of coastal ocean acidification: Perspectives from the Baltic-Skagerrak System	2019	Ambio	10.1007/s13280-018-1110-3
Salt marsh denitrification is impacted by oiling intensity six years after the Deepwater Horizon oil spill	2018	Environmental Pollution	10.1016/j.envpol.2018.09.034
Multiple Environmental Variables Affect Germination and Mortality of an Annual Salt Marsh Pioneer: <i>Salicornia procumbens</i>	2020	Estuaries and Coasts	10.1007/s12237-020-00735-y
The Role of Sea-Urchins in Marine Forests From Azores, Webbnesia, and Cabo Verde: Human Pressures, Climate-Change Effects and Restoration Opportunities	2021	Frontiers in Marine Science	10.3389/fmars.2021.649873
Effects of bottom trawling and primary production on the composition of biological traits in benthic assemblages	2018	Marine Ecology Progress Series	10.3354/meps12690

Long-term records of hard-bottom communities in the southwestern Baltic Sea reveal the decline of a foundation species	2019	Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science	10.1016/j.ecss.2019.02.029
Resource Occurrence and Productivity in Existing and Proposed Wind Energy Lease Areas on the Northeast US Shelf	2021	Frontiers in Marine Science	10.3389/fmars.2021.629230
Determinants of Tubastraea coccinea invasion and likelihood of further expansion in the northern Gulf of Mexico	2020	Marine Biodiversity	10.1007/s12526-020-01126-z
Above- and belowground responses to nutrient enrichment within a marsh-mangrove ecotone	2020	Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science	10.1016/j.ecss.2020.106884
Local and meso-scale pressures in the eutrophication process of a coastal subtropical system: Challenges for effective management	2021	Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science	10.1016/j.ecss.2020.107109
Submerged reefs in the Abrolhos Shelf: morphology and habitat distribution	2019	Seafloor Geomorphology as Benthic Habitat: GeoHab Atlas of Seafloor Geomorphic Features and Benthic Habitats	10.1016/B978-0-12-814960-7.00030-0
Phytoplankton assemblages of the subtropical south west Atlantic: Composition and dynamics in relation to physical and chemical processes	2018	Plankton Ecology of the Southwestern Atlantic: From the Subtropical to the Subantarctic Realm	10.1007/978-3-319-77869-3_7
The flourishing and vulnerabilities of zoantharians on Southwestern Atlantic reefs	2022	Marine Environmental Research	10.1016/j.marenvres.2021.105535
Temperature-Driven Growth Variation in a Deep-Sea Fish: The Case of Pagellus bogaraveo (Brünnich, 1768) in the Azores Archipelago	2021	Frontiers in Marine Science	10.3389/fmars.2021.703820
Evaluating quality of life, economic vulnerabilities, and drivers of ecosystem change	2004	Environmental Monitoring and Assessment	10.1023/B:EMAS.0000016880.31332.e1
Marine fisheries management in the Eastern Central Atlantic Ocean	2023	Ocean and Coastal Management	10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2023.106784
Meta-analysis reveals drivers of restoration success for oysters and reef community	2023	Ecological Applications	10.1002/eap.2865
Quantifying impacts of human pressures on ecosystem services: Effects of widespread non-indigenous species in the Baltic Sea	2023	Science of the Total Environment	10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.159975
Using long-term ecological monitoring to evaluate how climate and human-induced disturbances impact nekton communities in a Northern Gulf of Mexico estuary	2023	Hydrobiologia	10.1007/s10750-023-05206-6
Infaunal invertebrate community relationships to water column and sediment abiotic conditions	2024	Marine Biology	10.1007/s00227-023-04318-w
Evaluating coastal lagoon sustainability through the driver-pressure-state-impact-response approach: a study of Khenifiss Lagoon, southern Morocco	2024	Frontiers in Earth Science	10.3389/feart.2024.1322749
Local and global stressors as major drivers of the drastic regression of brown macroalgae forests in an oceanic island	2024	Regional Environmental Change	10.1007/s10113-024-02228-1
Building an integrated model for freshwater allocation with local managers in a coastal area	2012	iEMSs 2012 - Managing Resources of a Limited Planet: Proceedings of the 6th Biennial Meeting of the International Environmental	

		Modelling and Software Society	
Tradeoffs in habitat value to maximize natural resource benefits from coastal restoration in a rapidly eroding wetland: is monitoring land area sufficient?	2022	Restoration Ecology	10.1111/rec.13564
Old climatically-buffered infertile landscapes (OCBILs): more than harsh habitats, Atlantic Forest inselbergs can be drivers of evolutionary diversity	2022	Journal of Mountain Science	10.1007/s11629-021-7013-y
Alacranes reef: A refuge for structurally complex coral species from increasing stressors	2023	Ocean and Coastal Management	10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2023.106817
Drivers of trophodynamics of the open-ocean and deep-sea environments of the Azores, NE Atlantic	2024	Progress in Oceanography	10.1016/j.pocean.2024.103357
Temporal synchrony among juvenile marine fishes and potential climate and environmental drivers in the Bay of Biscay	2023	Progress in Oceanography	10.1016/j.pocean.2023.102969
Understanding sediment and carbon accumulation in macrotidal minerogenic saltmarshes for climate resilience	2024	Geomorphology	10.1016/j.geomorph.2024.109465